

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's views on social justice

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Positively my social philosophy may be said to be enshrined in three words: liberty, equality and fraternity."

"Man is not for religion, religion is for men."

"A religion which treats recognition of humanity as irreligion is not a religion but a disease."

Introduction:

Social justice is an important concept of society. Without this we have not idea of sustainable human being. Social justice is an application distributive justice to wealth asset privileges and advantages within a society or a state. Social justice involves removing inequalities in society and affording equal opportunities to all individuals in social economic and political affair of society. Indian society is divided into caste and communities, which create walls and barriers of exclusiveness within society on the basis of superiority and inferiority social justice in India is the product of injustice of the caste system. For B, R. Ambedkar, the concept of social justice for liberty, equality and fraternity for all human being. He advocated and social system on equalization in society among individuals in all spheres of life. He understood social political religious and economic problems as associated with caste and position of women in Indian society. His ideology and beliefs are important for social progress and stability of the Indian society. According he started the newspaper (Muknayak 1920) and advocate to the untouchable society's problems solution. He says 'newspaper is a instrument of social- movement' "Briefly dr. B.R. Ambedkar's social movement was social -justice. It's views on social -justice given below.

Objectives:

- 1) Understanding idea of social justice of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar.
- 2) Explain: social- justice and its relevance.
- 3) Understanding social justice and equality.

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4) Understanding which is factor of social -justice.

5) Social-justice is vast concept of society.

Research method:

About the research subject Dr. B.R. Ambedkar views on social justice, to clarify first of all use of method experimenters, observation and data collection. Also, from time to time published by the government report, it will be study and conclusion.

Beginning of the topic:

Dr B.R. Ambedkar was one of the most popular leaders in India. According to the Ambedkar's social-justice is a means to create an ideal or a just society.

The meaning of social justice:

The concept of social justice is broader than that of justice the word social is connected with society. Its scope is wide including social issues, problems and reforms thereby by it encompasses social and life economic change social justice clarify that no discrimination in society one man to another man about to be aspect of caste, creed, gender, language, race and religion etc. And adopt equality before law. At first presented by concept of social justice Plato (Ancient Greek philosopher). Plato his book 'The Republic' discusses the concept of justice through a Dialogue with friends. Like Cephalus, Polemarchus and Glaucon. Another Greek philosopher Aristotle he propounded the concept of distributive justice. John Rawls concept of social justice is all social primary goods liberty and opportunity, income and wealth and the basis of self-respect. Are to be distributed equally unless an unequal distribution of any or all of these goods is to the advantage of the least favored.(1).

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar beginning our social and political work from magnon conference (1920) meanwhile he started newspaper (Muk nayaka). In this newspaper he explained bad situation Hindu society include that cast and varna system. If the Hindu society there where ideal and sustainable so that totally abolished social and political in inequality. It's view's on like this all man is equal. He wrote "caste system is a dirty system and structure in Hindu society."(2) (Annihilation of caste 1936).

Once he said "the individual is an end in himself and that the aim and object of society is the growth of the individual and development of his personality. "The second essential is that the term of associated life

between member of society must be regarded by consideration founded on liberty, equality and fraternity.

(3) briefly social justice and self-development both are important every individual

. If you ask me my ideal would be a society based on liberty, equality and fraternity second time he says right are protected not by law but by the social and moral conscience of society"(4) accordingly thought of Babasaheb there has been relevance also now days. He supported to the right because every individual there will be not whole development of our life. He said "if social conscience is such that it is prepared to recognize the right which law choses to enact right will be safe and secure. But if the fundamental rights are opposed by the community no long no parliament no judiciary can guarantee than in the real sense of the word"

Cast does not result in economic efficiency caste cannot and has not improved the race case has however done one thing. It has completely disorganized and moralized the Hindu's. (5)

I think consequently of cast in Hindu society damaged. there was not equal position it means social and political inequality.

He said "about the social order the Hindu society. Hindu social system is undemocratic not by accident is designed to be undemocratic. It's division of society into varnas and castes and out cast is not theories also nowadays affected from caste and varna system every individual scheduled caste and tribes but are decrees. They are all very barricades raised against democracy (6)

Also, now days affected from cast and varna system every individual schedule caste and tribes. Similarly, untouchability is worst social problem. Accordance there were couldn't exist equal position in Indian society. Untouchability is may be mentioned is an institution or social practice that is the exclusive property of India and does not exist anywhere else in the world. In more than one sense it is an institution that is unnatural and runs counter to man psychology and social forces. ("7)

He expressed on class struggle "the problem at the untouchability is a matter of class struggle. It is a struggle between cast Hindu and the untouchable. This is not a matter of doing injustice against one man. This is a matter of injustice being done by one class against another. This class. Struggle has a relation with a social status this struggle indicates how one class should keep its relation with another class. This struggle starts as soon as you start climbing equal treatment with other (8).

We know any other society equal social status is important than any discrimination so that it may be solution Babasaheb effort time to time. Ahead this social background Dr. B.R. Ambedkar enter to the kalaram temple (1930 Nasik) he said "today we are about to enter the temple but the entry in the temple would not solve the whole problem. Our problem is comprehensive it is political, social, religious economic and educational.etc. the uses of kalaram temple entry is appeal to the Hindu mind the high caste Hindu deprived us from the for ages.

"Our real problem is not going to be solved by the entry in to ram temple it will not bring about me any radical change in our life but this is a test to judge the hi cast Hindu mind"(9)

He has to prove also we are people they there for the stage kalarm temple satyagraha. They like that there should be democracy in India because in this form of government asserted that liberty, equity, fraternity and justice. They says "the purpose of democracy is not so much to put a curb on an autocratic king but to bring about the welfare of the people. (10)

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar believe on democracy therefore whenever they wrote constitution of India provision to scheduled caste and tribes. For social justice to the represented fundamental rights and directive principals also important article ex:14,15, 16, 17, 21, 32, 340, 341, 342 etc.

About to conversion in Buddhism he said" that Yeola 13 October 1935 now we concluded that there is no change in attitude of the touchable. And they are not ready to be have with us with affection despite of our continuous struggle .as such we have decided to remain separate from Hindu to live with self-help and struggle to attain self-elevation. (11).

Conclusion:

About the discuss on research subject it turns out that today's relevance this subject social justice. Babasaheb was the only leader they comprehensively raised with the right for social justice his name is prominent figure in the history of modern India.

References

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